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#----- Modul Import-----#
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn import datasets, linear_model
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, r2_score
import matplotlib as mpl
import pandas as pd
from scipy import stats

#----- Parameters-----#
# SiO2_50      -32.09   mV
# SiO2_480    -52.42 mV
# SiO2_180    -21.37 mV
# SiO2_1200  -72.5   mV
# SiO2_100    -26.2
#Vs -> Zeta potential of surface
#Vp -> Zeta potential of Particles

Vs = np.zeros(5)

e0 = 8.85e-12 #vacum permitivity
ew = 78.5 #permitivity of water
Vs[0] = - 32.09e-3 # SiO2_50 (V)
Vs[1] = - 26.2e-3 # SiO2_100 (V)
Vs[2] = - 21.37e-3 # SiO2_180 (V)
Vs[3] = - 52.42e-3 # SiO2_480 (V)
Vs[4] = - 72.5e-3 # SiO2_1200 (V)
Vp = 60e-3 #(V)
# Rp = 240e-9
rs = 1e-15 #(m) approximated range of surface
rp = 1e-16 #(m) approximated range of particles
rd = 1e-18 #(m) approximated surface-particle distance

#----- Calculation of charges-----#
qs = np.zeros(5)
for i in range(0, 5):
    qs[i] = 4*np.pi*Vs[i]*e0*rs
    qp = 4*np.pi*Vp*e0*rp
    print(qs[i], qp)

#----- Calculation of Coulomb forces-----#
F = np.zeros(5)
for i in range(0, 5):
    F[i] = (1/(4*np.pi*e0*ew))*(qs[i]*qp/rd**2)
    print(F[i])

#----- calculating Hamaker constant for vdW interactions-----#

kb = 1.38064852e-23 #m2 kg s-2 K-1 boltzman constant
T = 298.14#temperature (kelvin)
ep = 3.9 #static dielectric constant of particles
es = 83 #static dielectric constant of substrate
nw = 1.3325 #refractive index of water
ns = 1.37 #refractive index of substrate
npa = 1.46 #refractive index of particles
nu = 1e9 #frequency (Hz)
h = 6.62607004e-34 #m2 kg / s planck constant
a1 = (es - ew)/(es + ew)
a2 = (ep - ew)/(ep + ew)
a3 = (ns**2 - nw**2)*(npa**2-nw**2)

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a4 = np.sqrt(ns**2 + nw**2)*np.sqrt(npa**2+nw**2)
a5 = np.sqrt(ns**2 + nw**2) + np.sqrt(npa**2+nw**2)
A = 0.75 * kb * T * a1 * a2 + (3*h*nu/(8*np.sqrt(2))) * (a3/(a4*a5))
print (A)

#-----Total forces including van der waals interactions-----#
def vdW (Rp) :
    W = A*Rp*1e-9/rd
    total = W + F
    total *=1e9
    return total

#-----Main programs-----#
mpl.use('pdf')

plt.close()
plt.rc('font', family='serif', serif='Times')
plt.rc('text', usetex=True)
plt.rc('xtick', labelsz=8)
plt.rc('ytick', labelsz=8)
plt.rc('axes', labelsz=8)

# width as measured in inkscape
width = 3.487
height = width / 1.618

fig, ax = plt.subplots()
fig, axarr = plt.subplots(1, figsize=(4,2), dpi=200, sharex=False, sharey=False)
fig.subplots_adjust(left=.15, bottom=.16, right=.99, top=.97)
colors= ['b', 'm', 'black', 'g', 'r', 'c', 'k', 'tab:olive']
markers = ['*', 'H', 'o', 'h', 'D', 'X', 's', 'v']

ax.set_ylabel(r'F$_{tot}$ [nN] ')
ax.set_xlabel('R$_{par}$ [nm]')

num = int((1201 - 50)/50.0)+1;
x = np.zeros((5, num))
y = np.zeros((5, num))
W = np.zeros((5, num))

for i in range (0, 5):
    m =0
    for j in range(50, 1201, 50):
        x[i, m] = j; #particle-size trials to obtain trend lines
        W[i, m] = A*x[i, m]*1e-9/(6*rd)
        total = W[i, m] + F[i]
        total *=1e9
        y[i, m] = total;
        m+=1

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a = np.zeros(5)
a [0] = 50
a [1] = 100
a [2] = 180

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a [3] = 480
a [4] = 1200

regr = linear_model.LinearRegression()
x1 = x[[0]]
y1 = y[[0]]
# print(x1)
# regr.fit(x1, y1)
# yn = regr.predict(x1)
slope = np.zeros(5)
intercept = np.zeros(5)
r_value = np.zeros(5)
p_value = np.zeros(5)
std_err = np.zeros(5)
xn = np.linspace(0,1200,1201)
yn = np.zeros((5, 1201))

#Determining slope and intercepts
for i in range(0,5):
    slope[i], intercept[i], r_value[i], p_value[i], std_err[i] = stats.linregress(x[[i]],y[[i]])
    yn[i] = slope[i]*xn+intercept[i]

#Applying trendline to the given parameters
b = np.zeros(5)
b [0] = slope[0]*50+intercept[0]
b [1] = slope[1]*100+intercept[1]
b [2] = slope[2]*180+intercept[2]
b [3] = slope[3]*480+intercept[3]
b [4] = slope[4]*1200+intercept[4]
print(a,b)
# for i in range(0,5):
#     axarr.scatter(x[i,:], y[i,:], s= 20, facecolors='none', edgecolors=colors[i], marker=markers[i],
# label='%d'%(i))
#     axarr.plot(xn, yn[i,:])
# axarr.plot(xn, line)
axarr.set_xlabel(r'R$_{par}$ [nm]')
axarr.set_ylabel(r'F$_{tot}$')
axarr.scatter(a, b)
fig.set_size_inches(width, height)
fig.savefig('vdW_size_dependence_var4.pdf',bbox_inches="tight", dpi=200)
plt.show()
plt.clf()

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